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ENDOMETRIAL CANCER: THE COMPLEXITY OF THE PROBLEM

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Abstract

This scientific and analytical work presents current global and local-regional data on incidence, mortality, lethality and five-year survival rate of such a common oncological pathology as endometrial cancer. It examines in detail the etiology and pathogenesis, modern approaches and principles of comprehensive diagnostics, prospects for improving treatment outcomes, and prognosis. The epidemiological characteristics of this disease in our republic are presented in the context of the country's regions.

Keywords: oncology, gynecology, endometrial cancer, risk factors, adenomyosis, endometriosis, human papillomavirus, DNA, mRNA, miRNA, lipid metabolism, microbiota, epidemiology, incidence, mortality, lethality, five-year survival rate, prognosis.

Cancer of the uterine body is a malignant tumor emanating from the mucous membrane of the uterine body (endometrium) [1]. In English-language literature, the term endometrial cancer (EC) is commonly used [2,3]. In most patients, EC is sporadic. In approximately 5% of cases, EC is associated with hereditary syndromes, particularly Lynch syndrome. Risk factors for this pathology include hyperestrogenism, early menarche, nulliparity, late menopause, age over 55, and tamoxifen use. There are two pathogenetic types of EC:

- Type I is more common. The tumor develops at a younger age, unlike patients with type II, due to prolonged hyperestrogenism and endometrial hyperplasia. Patients with type I ovarian tumors often have obesity, diabetes, and hypertension. They may also have estrogen-secreting ovarian tumors or sclerocystic ovary syndrome. Type I tumors are typically well-differentiated and have a more favorable prognosis.

- Type II. Endometrial tumors are usually poorly differentiated and have a less favorable prognosis. Type II tumors occur at an older age, in the absence of hyperestrogenism, and in the presence of endometrial atrophy.

Approximately 80% of patients with EC are diagnosed with endometrioid adenocarcinoma.

Uterine sarcomas include mesenchymal and mixed epithelial-mesenchymal tumors. Malignant mesenchymal tumors include leiomyosarcoma, endometrial stromal tumors, and related tumors. Mixed epithelial-mesenchymal tumors include adenosarcoma and carcinosarcoma. Genetic and molecular studies have demonstrated similarities in the molecular profiles of uterine carcinosarcoma and poorly differentiated endometrioid adenocarcinoma, suggesting an epithelial origin for the latter [1].

Diagnostic criteria include: Complaints of acyclic bloody, watery, or purulent discharge from the genital tract; bleeding during menopause. Anamnesis: the state of menstrual function (time of onset of first menstruation, duration of reproductive period, presence of acyclic uterine bleeding, characteristics of the course of menopause and time of onset of menopause) and reproductive function (attention is paid to the body weight of children born) are clarified; identification of metabolic disorders (obesity and diabetes mellitus) and cardiovascular pathology (hypertension).

Physical examination includes: gynecological examination [(condition of external genitalia; examination of the vagina and cervix using speculums (presence of vaginal infiltration, metastatic foci on the vaginal

walls, size, condition of the cervix); presence of pathological discharge (purulent, bloody)] and bimanual examination (size and shape of the uterus; condition of the appendages; infiltrates in the parametria; infiltration of the anterior and posterior vaginal fornix).

Laboratory diagnostic tests: cytological examination (increase in cell size up to giant, change in the shape and number of intracellular elements, increase in the size of the nucleus, its contours, different degrees of maturity of the nucleus and other cellular elements, change in the number and shape of nucleoli); histological examination (pronounced cellular polymorphism, increase in cell size, pronounced hypochromia, large nuclei contain one or more nucleoli, there are glandular structures of cancer cells in the form of rosettes, many cells in a state of mitosis); immunohistochemical examination of biopsy and surgical material (determination of the hormonal receptor status of estrogen and progesterone receptors in endometrial cancer and endometrial stromal sarcomas, determination of the morphological type of sarcomas); determination of tumor markers of the specific antigen CA 125 in the blood serum before the start of treatment; in case of an increase in the level before the start of specialized treatment, it can be used for dynamic observation and monitoring of the effectiveness of treatment; molecular genetic testing of microsatellite instability to determine the possibility of immunotherapy.

Instrumental studies: ultrasound of the pelvic organs (if endometrial cancer is suspected, the size of the uterus will be normal or enlarged, its structure is heterogeneous, the uterine cavity is deformed, the endometrium is enlarged; the condition of the cervix and ovaries is also assessed); ultrasound of the abdominal organs and retroperitoneal space (determination of metastatic lesions of the abdominal organs and retroperitoneal space); ultrasound Dopplerography of the lower limbs in female patients over 60 years of age before surgery to diagnose thrombophlebitis of the lower extremities; computed tomography of the chest, abdominal cavity and pelvis (assessment of the pelvic and retroperitoneal lymph nodes, organic changes in the chest and abdominal organs); magnetic resonance imaging of the pelvic organs (signs of endometrial cancer - an increase in the size of the uterus is noted, the outline is unclear, uneven; the structure of the myometrium is heterogeneous, diffusely nodular, fine- or coarse-grained; the endometrium is uneven, the border between the endometrium and the adjacent transition layer is unclear, uneven; the condition of the vagina, cervical canal, ovaries and adjacent tissues is also assessed); magnetic resonance imaging of the brain (performed in case of suspected metastatic brain damage); excretory urography (assessment of the position, shape, size, contours of the kidneys, the functional state of the kidneys, the shape and contours of the ureters and bladder); cystography (assessment of the shape, size and position of the bladder, determination of tumor penetration into the bladder and ureteral fistula); chest and abdominal radiography (mandatory determination of metastatic lesions of the chest organs); electrocardiography (mandatory examination during hospitalization in order to diagnose the presence of cardiac pathology to determine the possibility of specialized treatment);

echocardiography according to indications, taking into account age and cardiac history (in order to diagnose the presence of cardiac pathology to determine the possibility of specialized treatment); cystoscopy according to indications (in order to diagnose tumor penetration into the bladder); rectoscopy or colonoscopy according to indications (in order to diagnose the spread of the tumor process to the colon or rectum); skeletal scintigraphy (prescribed if bone metastases are suspected); positron emission tomography, positron emission tomography / computed tomography of the whole body (carried out to diagnose the prevalence of the tumor process in primary endometrial cancer or disease progression, or to assess the dynamics of the effectiveness of the special treatment) [4].

Although a variety of treatment modalities are used for endometrial cancer, including chemotherapy, targeted therapy, and radiation therapy in various regimens and combinations, both as combined and comprehensive treatments and as monotherapy, surgery remains the leading treatment option.

Given that surgery is the primary treatment for EC, robotic-assisted hysterectomy (RAH) is widely used in these patients [5].

Purpose of the procedure and intervention: RAH is performed to remove the tumor along with the uterus and cervix. Compared to traditional surgical interventions, RAH reduces the development of postoperative complications, shortens the patient's hospital stay, and reduces the risk of extensive bleeding. Contraindications to the procedure and intervention: the only absolute contraindication to RAH is anesthetic contraindication to pneumoperitoneum. Relative contraindications include the need for laparotomy to control bleeding, advanced malignancies, poor visualization in patients with multiple abdominal surgeries and adhesive disease. Patient comorbidities such as morbid obesity, acute ischemic or valvular heart disease, acute respiratory disease, or increased intracranial pressure are considered relative contraindications to the use of a robotic system. Women with asymptomatic uterine fibroids, with a low suspicion of malignancy, are not recommended for hysterectomy. Hysterectomy should not be recommended as a preventative measure against possible future fibroid growth. Indications for the procedure and intervention: RAH is performed in patients with endometrioid cancer stages I-III according to the FIGO classification. According to the guidelines of the National Comprehensive Cancer Network, RAH is the standard surgical treatment for early-stage cervical cancer according to the FIGO classification. Indications for hysterectomy include: women with uterine fibroids who have completed their childbearing function; rapid fibroid growth during menopause in women not using hormone replacement therapy (even in the absence of symptoms); suspected leiomyosarcoma. The choice of hysterectomy type, regardless of the approach (vaginal, laparoscopic, or laparotomic), should be based on the surgeon's experience, preferences, and the objective status of the patient (size and number of fibroid nodes, previous surgeries, extragenital pathology, etc.). Whenever possible, a minimally invasive approach to treatment is preferable [5].

The robotic surgical system consists of an open

surgical console, a laparoscopic column, and up to four robotic arms. The system's open platform configuration allows for the use of existing laparoscopic equipment. The system features 3D4K vision, eye tracking, an ergonomic surgical console, and haptic feedback. The instruments used are reusable, available with various jaw shapes, and are similar to laparoscopic instruments. Therefore, a surgeon with laparoscopic experience can easily adapt and use these instruments. Available instruments range in diameter from 3 to 10 mm, and all are re-sterilizable and reusable. Interactive "arms" are guided toward the patient lying on the operating table and attached to trocars. During a classic (straight) hysterectomy, a large incision is made in the lower abdomen, while during a RAH, only four small openings are made. Instruments are inserted through trocars, providing the operator with natural dexterity and a greater range of motion than the human hand. This ensures greater precision during manipulation in a minimally invasive environment. The operator works seated at the surgeon's console, located some distance from the operating table in a non-sterile area. A high-magnification, three-dimensional image provides unprecedented visualization of anatomical structures and virtually transports the surgeon's eyes and hands into the surgical field. Furthermore, the surgeon's comfort is ensured by the seated position, armrests, an ergonomically designed stereoscopic eyepiece port that provides support for the operator's head and neck, the design of the main controllers, and adjustable eyepiece height and interocular distance. This facilitates surgical procedures and accelerates learning and acquisition of manual skills. The total duration of the surgery is approximately 4 hours and is performed in several stages. The duration of the surgery was calculated by summing the results of various studies and calculating an average value. The surgical team generally consists of five people and includes the operating surgeon, an assisting surgeon, an anesthesiologist, a scrub nurse, and a sanitary worker. The technique of laparoscopic RAH is performed using a method adapted from robotic systems.

The technique for performing RAH is as follows [5]:

- 1) Preparation of the patient and placement of troacports. The patient is placed on the table in the dorsal lithotomy position (supine position with the hips and knees fully flexed, legs apart and raised, and feet resting on straps. Soft pads are placed under the patient's arms and adjusted to the torso. Preoperative prophylactic antibiotics are administered. A Veress needle is prepared to create pneumoperitoneum. The operation is performed under general anesthesia. Troacports of the robotic system are installed. A total of 5 ports can be installed, ranging in size from 3 to 10 mm. Traditionally, an approach using 4 troacports is used. The first troacport is installed at the navel and is intended for a robotic camera. The second and third ports are intended for robotic laparoscopic instruments and are installed to the left and right of the first port each (the distance between the troacports is 8 mm). The fourth additional troacport is also intended for the use of instruments and is installed below the left port (the distance between Troacports – 8 mm).

- 2) The operating surgeon moves to the surgical

console, the surgical assistant and the operating nurse stand by the patient. The assisting surgeon operates the laparoscopic instruments, and the operating nurse delivers surgical instruments and materials. The anesthesiologist monitors the patient's condition under anesthesia. The uteroovarian ligament is dissected using a bipolar instrument. Care should be taken with the parametric vessels.

- 3) The bladder is mobilized. The round ligament is divided, and the anterior and posterior layers of the broad ligament are separated. The vesicouterine pouch is then identified, and the incision is continued anteriorly, thereby mobilizing the bladder from the lower uterine segment.

- 4) The descending uterine artery is dissected with a bipolar instrument at the level of the internal cervix.

- 5) The uterus and cervix are separated from the vaginal angle. The uterus is removed. A vaginal stump is formed.

- 6) The surgical wound is closed, a catheter is inserted into the urethra, the trocars are disconnected and removed, and the wound is sutured. A sanitary worker cleans the operating room.

Indicators of the procedure's effectiveness: low blood loss, no indications for blood transfusion, no intraoperative complications; wound healing by primary intention, suture integrity, a dry and clean postoperative wound; laboratory tests: no elevated leukocytosis, leukocyturia is acceptable, and a moderate decrease in hemoglobin and red blood cell levels.

Risk factors of ECs include high body mass index (BMI) or obesity (BMI > 30), diabetes, hypertension, prolonged exposure to oestrogen (menarche at a young age, nulliparity and infertility, menopause at an older age, and polycystic ovarian syndrome), and use of tamoxifen. Women with Lynch syndrome have a high lifetime risk of EC, and those women are thus recommended to be enrolled in a surveillance programme [6].

Li W. et al. [7] in their study note that endometrial carcinoma (EC) has become one of the most common gynecological malignant neoplasms in developed countries worldwide. Studies have shown that this may be closely related to the abnormal metabolism of blood lipids, which was the most significant metabolic change in the human body in this cancer.

In this study, the authors focused on the correlation between lipid metabolism and endometrial cancer (EC) and discussed the evidence that abnormal lipid metabolism promotes an increase in EC growth and metabolism, as well as the regulatory mechanism and related signaling pathways involved in this relationship.

The obtained results highlight the significant role played by various factors, such as low levels of high-density lipoprotein, high levels of total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein, triglycerides, and obesity, in both the development and progression of EC.

These factors contribute to a poorer prognosis for EC patients. Therefore, it is clinically possible to identify EC patients at an early stage by measuring serum lipid levels. This early detection enables patients to receive early treatment, reducing the risk of tumor metastasis and ultimately improving the prognosis of EC. In clinical practice, the initial prognosis of EC patients can

also be assessed by evaluating serum lipid levels. The more severe the disorder of lipid metabolism, the poorer the prognosis for EC. In addition, our colleagues identified the potential benefits of lipid-modifying statins as adjunctive therapy in EC. Statins have shown promise in improving patient prognosis and reducing mortality rates. However, extensive clinical trials and mechanistic studies are needed to establish the true effectiveness of statins in the treatment of EC.

The authors emphasize that in recent years, increasing evidence has shown that dyslipidemia is strongly associated with the development and progression of EC, but the underlying etiologic link between dyslipidemia and EC is less well understood. Although the exact biological mechanisms and pathophysiological events have not been fully investigated, the potential mechanisms, including different types of dyslipidemia, obesity, inflammation, angiogenesis, estrogen metabolism, and other specific activation of signaling pathways involved, may give rise to an excess risk of EC in patients with abnormal lipid metabolism [7].

In his work, Zakrzewski P.K. [8] says that endometrial cancer is one of the most common malignancies of the female reproductive system, with incidence rising globally due to population ageing and life-style-related risk factors. Calcium (Ca^{2+}) is a ubiquitous second messenger regulating diverse physiological processes, and its dysregulation has been increasingly implicated in carcinogenesis, including endometrial. Altered expression and function of Ca^{2+} channels, pumps, exchangers, and binding proteins disrupt the finely tuned balance of Ca^{2+} influx, efflux, and intracellular storage, leading to aberrant signalling that promotes tumour proliferation, migration, survival, and metastasis. This review summarises current knowledge on the molecular “ Ca^{2+} toolkit” in the human uterus, highlighting the role of voltage-gated calcium channels, transient receptor potential channels, store-operated calcium entry components, $\text{Na}^{+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchangers, purinergic receptors, P-type ATPases (SERCA, SPCA, PMCA), ryanodine and inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate receptors, and mitochondrial Ca^{2+} uniporter complexes in endometrial cancer progression. Multiple Ca^{2+} -handling proteins, including CACNA1D, CACNA2D1, TRPV4, TRPV1, TRPM4, MCU, and RyR1, exhibit cancer-associated overexpression or functional changes, correlating with poor prognosis and aggressive disease features. Emerging evidence supports the therapeutic potential of targeting Ca^{2+} homeostasis using small-molecule inhibitors, ion channel modulators or gene-silencing strategies. These interventions may restore Ca^{2+} balance, induce apoptosis or autophagy, and suppress metastatic behaviour. While no clinical trials have yet explicitly focused on Ca^{2+} modulation in endometrial cancer, the diversity of dysregulated Ca^{2+} pathways offers a rich landscape for novel therapeutic strategies. Targeting key components of the Ca^{2+} signalling network holds promise for improving outcomes in endometrial cancer.

In their study, the authors showed that deregulation of the cellular calcium machinery is a recurring feature in endometrial cancer. The observed alterations

in calcium signalling are reported across various cellular compartments and involve a wide range of transporters, channels, and pumps localised in the plasma membrane, sarcoplasmic/endoplasmic reticulum, and mitochondrial membranes. Dysregulated expression or function of these components can disrupt the tightly controlled balance of calcium influx and efflux, leading to aberrant intracellular calcium dynamics that contribute to cancer proliferation, migration, survival, and resistance to therapy. Targeting these dysregulated components may enable selective modulation of calcium signalling pathways that are essential for tumour growth and resistance to apoptosis. This opens the possibility for developing more precise, mechanism-based treatment strategies for endometrial cancer, including small-molecule inhibitors, ion channel modulators, targets of the endocannabinoid system or gene-silencing approaches, aimed at restoring calcium homeostasis and inhibiting disease progression. An interesting direction in developing new therapies for oestrogen-dependent endometrial cancer involves using calcium channel blockers alongside anti-oestrogen drugs as adjuvant treatments. Moreover, the limited literature data regarding the involvement of calcium homeostasis components, such as SERCA, SPCA, STIM, or transient receptor potential channels, in the development and progression of endometrial cancer should not deter further research. Instead, it should indicate potential new directions for studies on therapeutic targets based on these hitherto unexplored proteins involved in maintaining proper intracellular Ca^{2+} levels in endometrial cancer [8].

As Sobstyl M. et al. [9] note in their study, the female reproductive tract hosts a specific microbiome, which plays a crucial role in sustaining equilibrium and good health. In the majority of reproductive women, the microbiota (all bacteria, viruses, fungi, and other single-celled organisms within the human body) of the vaginal and cervical microenvironment are dominated by *Lactobacillus* species, which benefit the host through symbiotic relationships, in comparison to the uterus, fallopian tubes, and ovaries, which may contain a low-biomass microbiome with a diverse mixture of microorganisms. Although disruption to the balance of the microbiota develops, the altered immune and metabolic signaling may cause an impact on diseases such as cancer. These pathophysiological modifications in the gut - uterus axis may spark gynecological cancers. New information displays that gynecological and gastrointestinal tract dysbiosis (disruption of the microbiota homeostasis) can play an active role in the advancement and metastasis of gynecological neoplasms, such as cervical, endometrial, and ovarian cancers. Understanding the relationship between microbiota and endometrial cancer is critical for prognosis, diagnosis, prevention, and the development of innovative treatments. Identifying a specific microbiome may become an effective method for characterization of the specific microbiota involved in endometrial carcinogenesis.

The analysis allowing for the exploration of the discussed topic was carried out on the basis of information gathered from two databases: PubMed and Web of Science. Initial identification of the articles was based on a keyword search for “endometrial cancer”,

“Endometrium”, and “Cancer”. Duplicate entries from both databases were rejected. Then, the list of publications was narrowed down by using appropriate filters. The first was the year the article was published, using the 2000-2022 range. The second criterion was the type of publication, which included clinical trials, reviews, and systematic reviews (all duplicate items were rejected). Then, for further analysis, only articles of which the full text was available, and containing such keywords as “microbiota”, “microbiome”, “immune system”, or “immune response”, were selected. After filtering the data, there were 90 articles that met the above criteria. The possibility of including each work for publication was thoroughly assessed. Additionally, 34 works on statistical and epidemiological information were included, as well as issues indicated by reviewers. Ultimately, 124 articles were included in the review. Based on the conducted research, the authors concluded that to date, the structure of the endometrial hyperplasia microbiome can be distinguished from that of the benign uterine state, suggesting either a role of the microbiome in the early stages of cellular transformation or a well-known response to changes in the physiological or chemical gradient in the host cell. Additionally, the uterine microbiome can stimulate the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines in endometrial cells, including IL-1 α , IL-1 β , IL-17 α , and TNF- α , which are involved in the carcinogenesis of various cancers. Due to the estrogen-dependent nature of endometrial cancer, dysbiosis of not only of the uterus, but also the intestinal microflora, is indirectly involved in carcinogenesis, causing an increase in serum estrogen levels by reactivating estrogen metabolites. Mechanical studies using *in vitro* and *in vivo* models, along with animal models, are necessary to determine the role of the microflora and specific bacterial species in initiating and/or maintaining cancer in the female reproductive system, including the uterus. In the therapeutic setting, there is a significant interest and demand to diagnose and improve endometrial dysfunctions in order to treat uterine dysbiosis, despite the fact that there is no standardized technique for testing the endometrial microbial composition, nor for treating uterine dysbiosis. New therapies, such as probiotic and prebiotic supplements and microbiota transplants, are still poorly understood, and there are insufficient data to support the use of probiotics for enhancing and maintaining the appropriate microbiota composition. Advances in macrobiotics and metagenomics have allowed researchers to begin identifying microbial communities and/or specific bacterial species that can cause pathological conditions in the female reproductive tract and, thus, contribute to the development and progression of cancer. Nevertheless, in the future, clinical trials with larger cohorts are required to validate and extend these initial findings to potential clinical use, as illustrated in the International Cancer Microbiome Consortium’s 2019 statement that long-term cohort data are required to support the role of the human microbiome as a critical driver of cancer’s etiopathogenesis. In addition, future epidemiological research must include women of different races, age groups, ethnicities, and socioeconomic status, as significant differences in the composition of the vaginal mi-

croflora have been identified between women of different ethnic origins. Additionally, it seems necessary to explain the influence of endometrial microbiome biodiversity on the reproductive process and the commensal or pathogenic relationships between microorganisms and endometrial cells. Furthermore, scientists should also look for answers to questions about the mechanisms of bacterial colonization and survival in the endometrial environment, and the actions of signaling pathways potentially activated by these microorganisms (with particular emphasis on the metabolites they synthesize). Only with an interdisciplinary and comprehensive approach to the issue of the role of the immune system and changes in the endometrial and uterine microbiota will it be possible to understand how their mutual correlation contributes to the development and progression of gynecological neoplasms [9].

An interesting study was conducted by Karachaliou C. et al. [10]. The authors note that chronic human papillomavirus (HPV) infection has not been clearly established as the protagonist of upper female genital tract carcinogenesis. Malignancies of the female upper reproductive tract, especially endometrial and ovarian cancers, generate a significant burden for women worldwide. The possible etiopathogenetic role of chronic HPV infection in the carcinogenesis of the female upper genital tract is neither clearly established nor completely understood. Therefore, our colleagues performed a literature review, using the PubMed and Scopus electronic databases, of the prevalence of HPV DNA in endometrial, primary fallopian tube, ovarian, and primary peritoneal cancers, as well as uterine sarcomas. The present investigation covered 35 studies from different countries on various continents. Overall, the prevalence of HPV was approximately 15% in all the above cancers. HPV DNA was isolated from 11%, 0%, 0%, and 14% of endometrial carcinomas, uterine sarcomas, primary fallopian tube cancers, and ovarian malignant neoplasms, respectively. No relevant studies on primary peritoneal cancers were retrieved. The predominant HPV strain from tumors of the upper female reproductive tract, regardless of the tumor site, was HPV-16, followed by HPV-18. The HPV DNA identified was exclusively from subtypes HPV-6, HPV-11, HPV-16, HPV-18, and HPV-33, which are responsible for the development of not only cervical cancer, but also condylomata acuminata. The findings of the present review indicate that HPV vaccination might prove to be a useful strategy in the prevention of HPV-related carcinomas of the upper genital tract in women.

The presence of HPV DNA in EC was examined in 24 studies, i.e., 5 case-control studies, 17 case series, and 2 case reports, which included a total of 668 patients with EC. Endometrioid endometrial carcinomas were the most frequent histological type recorded. Viral DNA was detected in 15 of 24 studies (62%) and in 74 patients (74/668; 11%). HPV DNA positivity ranged from 0 to 100%. DNA from HPV-16 was isolated from 29 patients, making this the most common HPV subtype (29/74; 39%). The rest of the HPV strains detected were HPV-6, HPV-18, HPV-33, HPV-11, and HPV-31, which were found in 20, 12, 8, 3, and 2 EC specimens, respectively. In the present review, ECs prevalence, regardless of type, was approximately 11%, ranging from

0% to 100%. Endometrioid EC was the most common histological type studied and HPV-16 was the most frequent HPV subtype found. An important aspect of HPV-related endometrial carcinogenesis involves the route of HPV's transmission from the lower female genital tract to the upper female reproductive tract. The former includes the vagina and the ectocervix, is covered with multiple layers of stratified squamous epithelia, and is often exposed to pathogens. The latter, which includes the uterus, endometrium, and endocervix, consists of a single layer of columnar epithelium that maintains a relatively sterile environment, with intermittent microorganisms ascending from the lower female genital tract. The endocervix functions as an interface between the relatively sterile upper female reproductive tract and the non-sterile lower female genital tract. It is hypothesized that HPVs could ascend to the endometrium from the vagina and the ectocervix through the endocervix and infect the squamous epithelium in the endometrium. It is in a similar fashion that HPV infects the basal cells of the squamous epithelium in the cervix. HPV DNA isolation from the upper female genital tract varies widely among the published studies. Nevertheless, the presence of both high-risk and low-risk HPV subtypes in anatomical sites above the cervix implicates their potential role in the development of cancer at these sites. However, a more sensitive detection method, based on mRNA HPV oncogene expression instead of HPV DNA isolation, could compare the viral oncogene expression in malignant tissue samples with that in adjacent healthy tissues, thus further clarifying the potential role of HPVs in tumorigenesis in the upper female reproductive tract. Moreover, there is no strong evidence of whether HPV vaccines could lower the incidence of these malignant neoplasms. Not only prospective multicenter studies on the incidence of HPV DNA-positive malignant tumors in HPV-vaccinated versus HPV-unvaccinated women, but also large-sample retrospective studies on the prevalence of HPV vaccination in HPV DNA-positive malignancies of the upper female reproductive tract, could shed further light on the potentially protective role of HPV vaccines against carcinogenesis in the corpus uteri, adnexa, and peritoneum. The present comprehensive review demonstrated that HPV DNA can be found in both endometrial carcinomas and ovarian cancer cases. Highly oncogenic HPV-16 and HPV-18 were the most common HPV strains identified in the majority of the studies. Therefore, the necessity of HPV vaccination for women and men remains imperative in ensuring that a significant reduction in the incidence and burden of HPV-related malignancies of the upper female genital tract is achieved worldwide [10].

Diseases such as adenomyosis and endometriosis deserve special attention.

Szibert M. et al. [11] in their work they say that adenomyosis, endometriosis, and gynecological cancers, such as endometrial, ovarian endometrioid, and clear cell cancers, may have common pathogenetic mechanisms that, amongst others, include hormonal factors, genetic predisposition growth factors, inflammation, altered function of the immune system, environmental factors, and oxidative stress. Adenomyosis is a common benign gynecological condition, defined

as an extension of endometrial tissue into the myometrium. Some studies suggest that adenomyosis could be a favorable prediction factor associated with survival outcomes in endometrial cancer.

In this study, the authors systematized the current knowledge about different types of interconnections between adenomyosis and endometrial cancer or other cancers of women's reproductive systems. They also studied possible molecular mechanisms of carcinogenesis in adenomyotic lesions. In addition, the long-term prognosis for patients with endometrial cancer and co-existing adenomyosis (and endometriosis) was a key point of this research. The researchers performed advanced searches for PubMed literature using the phrases: "adenomyosis and endometrial cancer" and "malignant transformation of adenomyosis". From 545 citations covering the period 1954-2020, 470 articles were initially excluded after title, abstract or content screening by two independent authors. The next 26 articles were excluded after a full text screening and during data collection. Finally, 39 articles were included for the analysis. Details of the results retrieved are shown according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines.

Our colleagues note that adenomyosis has been frequently observed in hysterectomy specimens for endometrial adenocarcinoma. In addition, adenomyosis may be a potential risk factor for the development of myometrial or endometrial neoplasms.

Adenomyosis and endometriosis are known as estrogen-dependent benign diseases, with common molecular pathways. Both these conditions may undergo a malignant transformation. However, in the case of endometriosis, the possible molecular mechanisms of carcinogenesis are well described. Carcinomas derived from endometriosis have been well established; histological subtype, epidemiologic endometriosis associated ovarian cancer risk was identified. On the contrary, the neoplastic potential in adenomyosis is poorly understood, and has been mainly described in association with EC. The coincidence between these two diseases can be an effect of potential common risk factors, which may lead to hyper-estrogenic status (history of diabetes, hypertension, high BMI, and tamoxifen intake, but not nulliparity) or by shared pathogenetic mechanisms, including genetic mutation and inflammatory factors that induce angiogenesis and cell proliferation, which promote carcinogenesis [11,12].

According to the presented data, adenomyosis seems to be a favorable prognostic oncological factor when it occurs with EC, but the finding appears to be contradictory. EC Arising In Adenomyosis is a rare phenomenon, but it is associated with higher malignancy and nodal metastasis risk. It is necessary to validate the process of detection of adenomyosis in an intraoperative frozen section for assessing the necessity for lymphadenectomy. Considering this, more caution may be required when selecting the most appropriate histopathological confirmation of adenomyosis and surgical treatment for patients with hyper-estrogenic status and with risk factors, regardless of potential malignant transformations in adenomyosis. In clinical practice, early, more effective recognition and precise

standards in ultrasonography to identify adenomyosis are required. Implementing Morphological Uterus Sonographic Assessment standards could lead to higher diagnosis rates of adenomyosis [11].

The researchers emphasize that prospective large-scale cohort studies investigating the risk of malignant transformation of adenomyosis are needed. Prospective studies focused on the life risk of malignant transformation should be undertaken to prove which women should undergo a definitive treatment of adenomyosis. There is a need to elaborate the “decision making tree” in patients with adenomyosis towards radical treatment, especially in patients with hormone-replacement therapy or endocrine treatment of breast cancer or other risk factors of EC, such as obesity, diabetes, and hypertension. In the future, algorithms including all available prognostic values - genetic mutation, in this respect Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog - KRAS mutation as a factor for efficacy of hormonal therapy; ultrasound features (depth of myometrial invasion); and clinical characteristics (age, concomitant disease, BMI) - might lead to the individualized management of patients with adenomyosis, with a possible malignant transformation of adenomyosis into cancer [11].

Iavarone I. et al. [13] conducted a study aims to examine the distribution and the regulation of the differentially expressed miRNAs and extracellular vesicles derived substances in women with endometrial cancer. The authors emphasize that an extracellular vesicle is part of a class of submicron particles derived from cells, mediating cellular crosstalk through microRNA (miRNA). MiRNA is a group of RNA molecules, each of which consists of 15-22 nucleotides and post-transcriptionally modulates gene expression. The complementary mRNAs - onto which the miRNAs hybridize - are involved in processes such as implantation, tumor suppression, proliferation, angiogenesis, and metastasis that define the entire tumor microenvironment. The endometrial biopsy is a standard technique used to recognize cellular atypia, but other non-invasive markers may reduce patient discomfort during the use of invasive methods.

The methods for this work were specified a priori on the basis of the recommendations in the PRISMA statement. A systematic search was performed for articles in the PubMed database, Embase, Cochrane Library, ScienceDirect, and Scopus database in April 2023 using the string “Endometrial Neoplasms AND Exosomes”. There were no restrictions on the year of publication or the country of origin, and only articles published in English were taken into account. The inclusion criteria were the following: (1) studies that included patients with EC and described miRNA regulation in the context of that neoplasm; (2) studies reporting the outcome of interest, such as miRNA regulation in EC, and its clinical implication; and (3) all peer-reviewed articles that were originally published. The researchers excluded preclinical trials, unoriginal studies, animal trials, articles in languages other than English, and abstract-only publications. When possible, authors of different studies that were only published as conference abstracts were contacted through e-mail and asked to show their final results. Our colleagues men-

tioned all selected studies and the reasons for their exclusion in the PRISMA flowchart. They also assessed all the studies concerning potential conflicts of interest. After the database search, 86 studies matched the search criteria. After deleting duplicates and records with no full-text and incorrect study designs (e.g., reviews), 19 were eligible. Of those, 11 matched the inclusion criteria and were included in the final systematic review schema. Seven articles were prospective case-control studies evaluating miRNA expression in patients and controls; two records were prospective cohort studies; and two articles were retrospective studies. The publication years ranged from 2015 to 2021. A total of 371 patients with EC and 273 controls were included. The FIGO stage of disease ranged from I to IV. The upregulated molecules that had the widest delta between endometrial cancer patients and controls - relative expression $\geq 1 > 3 \log_2(\text{ratio})$ - were miR-20b-5p, miR-204-5p, miR-15a-5p, and miR-320a. In particular, miR-20b-5p and miR-204-5p were extracted from both serum and endometrial specimens, whereas miR-15a-5p was only isolated from plasma, and miR-320a was only extracted from the endometrial specimens. In parallel, the most downregulated miRNA in the endometrial cancer patients compared to the healthy subjects was miR-320a, which was found in the endometrial specimens [13].

In conclusion, the authors emphasize that many recent studies have demonstrated that intercellular crosstalk is crucially important in EC, even though data in the literature are heterogeneous. A panel of miRNAs could be feasible for the early detection and progression of disease in EC-affected patients using liquid and endometrial biopsies even though there is a lack of evidence showing that differentially expressed miRNAs can be used as biomarkers to guide various treatment protocols. Although pathways of epigenetic regulation are unclear, the evaluation of miRNA expression is a valuable and cost-effective option in the diagnosis of EC. Further evidence is needed to clarify miRNA regulation during the remission, relapse, and progression of EC to facilitate the planning of a targeted disease management strategy. Though miRNA epigenetic regulation remains unknown, these upregulated molecules derived from EV extracellular vesicles derived are feasible markers for the early detection of endometrial cancer. The modulation of these miRNA molecules should be assessed during different treatments or if recurrence develops in response to a targeted treatment modality [13].

Now, regarding this pathology in our country at the national level. The incidence of EC in the Republic of Kazakhstan in 2023 was 6.9 per 100,000 population (6.7 in 2022) with a growth rate of 2.2% compared to the previous year, amounting to 1,371 people in absolute numbers (1,315 women – a year earlier). The proportion of cases with a first-time diagnosis, recorded by oncology organizations, was 3.70% (3.75% – a year earlier) in the general population, and 6.6% among women (in 2022 also 6.6%) and 3rd place after breast cancer and cervical cancer [14].

EC incidence rates above the national average were established in 10 regions of the country: in the Karaganda region – 14.6 (the maximum indicator); East

Kazakhstan - 14.4; North Kazakhstan - 14.1; Ulytau - 13.5; Kostanay - 11.6; Pavlodar - 11.1; the city of Almaty - 8.4; Akmola - 8.1; West Kazakhstan - 8.0; Abay - 7.1. This indicator is also below the national average in 10 regions: Turkestan - 2.6 (the lowest level); Atyrau - 3.0; Zhambyl - 3.5; Mangistau - 3.6; the city of Shymkent - 4.0; Kyzylorda - 4.2; Almaty - 4.6; the city of Astana - 4.7; Aktobe - 6.0 and Zhetysu - 6.6 regions per 100 thousand people. The mortality rate from this pathology in 2023 was 1.3 per 100,000 people (in 2022, it was 1.2), with a growth rate of 8.6%, amounting to 267 women in absolute numbers (compared to 241 patients the previous year).

The regions with the EC mortality rate above the national average (1.3 per 100,000 population) are: Abay - 2.8 (maximum level); East Kazakhstan - 2.7; Karaganda - 2.6; North Kazakhstan - 2.4; Pavlodar - 2.1; Akmola - 1.9; Kostanay - 1.6; the city of Shymkent - 1.5. This indicator is on par with the national average in Aktobe, Mangistau regions and the city of Almaty. The lowest indicators were noted in Turkestan and Ulytau regions - 0.5 (minimum indicator); as well as in Atyrau, Zhetysu and West Kazakhstan regions - 0.7; Zhambyl region and the city of Astana - 0.9; Almaty - 1.1, Kyzylorda regions - 1.2, and per 100,000 population [14].

One-year lethality rate was 7.2% (7.9% in 2022). Moreover, the ratio between one-year lethality and the severity of the disease (stage IV) was quite high – 1.7 (the year before, it was even higher – 2.1). However, it should be noted that the farthest from "1" is the worst ratio between one-year lethality and severity of the disease.

Now, regarding preventive examinations. It should be noted that during large-scale preventive examinations of the population in 2023, significantly more patients with malignant neoplasms were actively identified than in 2022. This is 25,193 patients versus 23,623 patients identified in 2022, i.e. +6.6%. This is due to the further easing of the epidemiological situation due to the coronavirus and the increased availability of preventive care for the population. The proportion of patients identified during preventive examinations increased from 62.0% to 62.4% of the total number of patients identified during the year.

Of course, with early diagnosis rates are crucial in analyzing the epidemiological situation. Overall, of all cancer cases detected across all sites, the proportion of cases detected at early stages (stages 0, I-II) increased from 66.3% to 67.9% in 2023.

As for EC, the early detection rate of this pathology during preventive examinations decreased from 82.5% to 78.5% (in absolute numbers, 1,053 women were diagnosed in 2023, which is 6 more than in 2022 (1,047 women). The number of newly diagnosed EC patients registered with oncology organizations amounted to 1,341 (1,269 in the previous year). At the same time, the percentage of patients diagnosed with stages I-II of the disease increased from 86.6% (in 2022) to 87.3% (in 2023), or 907 and 919 women, respectively.

The regions with the proportion of patients with early stage I of the pathology in question above the national average (67.2% and a high 3rd rank among all

nosological forms of malignant neoplasms) include the following: East Kazakhstan - 92.1% (the best indicator); followed by: Aktobe - 85.5%; the city of Astana - 81.5%; West Kazakhstan - 79.6%; Karaganda - 78.1%; Atyrau - 75.0%; the city of Almaty - 72.9%; Zhambyl - 71.4%; Kyzylorda - 68.6%; North Kazakhstan - 67.6%.

The lowest rates of early diagnosis were recorded in 10 regions. Against this background, two regions stand out – Turkestan and the city of Shymkent, where stage I disease prevalence was established in only 21.4% and 33.3%, respectively (the worst indicators in the republic). They are followed by: Abay - 51.2%; Pavlodar - 51.8%; Kostanay - 55.9%; Zhetysu - 57.8%; Ulytau - 60.0%; Mangistau - 60.7%; Almaty - 64.3%; Akmola - 66.7% of the regions [14].

It should be noted that in the early (I-II) stages, this pathology was detected in 84.3% of the republic, and this is the 6th rank among all nosological forms of malignant tumors.

The regions where the proportion of patients with EC, identified at stages I-II, is above the national average include the following regions. The best indicator was shown by Mangistau region - 96.4%. It is followed by: East Kazakhstan (95.0%); Zhetysu (91.1%); Ulytau (90.0%); Aktobe (89.1%); Pavlodar (88.0%); the city of Almaty (87.3%); Zhambyl and Turkestan (85.7%); West Kazakhstan (85.2%); the city of Astana (84.6%). Low rates of early diagnosis were recorded in the following regions. The city of Shymkent stands out against the general background, where only three out of every five patients were detected in the early stages of the disease - 64.6%. Next come: Almaty (72.9%); Kyzylorda (77.1%); North Kazakhstan (78.4%); Abay (79.1%); Atyrau (80.0%); Kostanay (81.7%); Karaganda (83.2%); Akmola (84.1%) regions [14].

As the above data clearly demonstrates, there is a significant range in early diagnosis rates across the country, from good to disappointing. While migration and other factors influencing early diagnosis rates must certainly be taken into account, the results obtained provide a reason for oncologists and gynecologic oncologists, as well as obstetricians and gynecologists, imaging specialists, and general practitioners, to continue to strive for improvement. Improving early diagnosis rates for malignant tumors remains a fundamental tenet and a key objective of medicine as a whole, and remains a pressing issue today.

The proportion of stage IV EC among all malignant neoplasms was 4.1%, ranking 23rd. Overall, in 2023, the proportion of stage IV malignant neoplasms across the country, across all nosologies, decreased from 12.58 to 11.7% (from 4,790 to 4,735 patients).

As for the national average for the proportion of stage IV (4.1%), Aktobe, Mangystau, and Ulytau regions stand out with 0.0%. Then come: Pavlodar (1.2%); Turkestan (1.8%); Kyzylorda and Almaty (2.9%); East Kazakhstan (3.0%); Akmola (3.2%), and the city of Almaty (3.9%). The following regions have lower rates. The city of Shymkent stands out, with 12.5% of patients diagnosed in the terminal stage of the disease. Next come: North Kazakhstan (8.1%); Zhambyl (7.1%); Abay (7.0%); West Kazakhstan (5.6%); Atyrau (5.0%); the city of Astana (4.6%); Karaganda (4.5%); Zhetysu (4.4%) and Kostanay (4.3%)

regions.

The morphological verification rate of the disease in the country was 97.5%. In 11 regions out of 20, this figure was 100% (Abay, Almaty, Atyrau, East Kazakhstan, Zhambyl, West Kazakhstan, Mangistau, North Kazakhstan Ulytau regions, as well as the cities of Astana and Shymkent). The lowest rate was in Kyzylorda region (82.9%). Next on this list were Akmola (88.9%); Zhetysay (93.3%); the city of Almaty (93.4%); Turkestan and Aktobe (98.2%); Pavlodar (98.8%); Kostanay (98.9%) and Karaganda (99.4%) regions [14].

The total number of patients with malignant neoplasms registered with specialized oncology organizations in the republic continued to increase and by the end of 2023 amounted to 218,186 people, an increase of 6.0% compared to the previous year (2022 – 205,822, +5.8%). The overall incidence rate of malignant neoplasms increased by 3.9%, from 1,055.3 to 1,096.4 per 100,000 population. This increase is due to both the increased incidence and detection of pathology, and the increased survival rate of cancer patients. Furthermore, statistical data on patients diagnosed with malignant neoplasms who have been under observation for 5 years or more and who continue to be monitored in 2023 showed that the number of patients under observation by oncology organizations in Kazakhstan for over five years continued to grow and at the end of the reporting year amounted to 117,616 people, an increase of 6.2% (2022 – 110,790 people, +6.6%) (Form No. 7).

An important clinical aspect, such as the coverage of patients diagnosed with EC for the first time in their lives with specialized treatment in the Republic of Kazakhstan, cannot be ignored. In 2023, the number of hospitalizations for all types of malignant tumors in oncology organizations across the country amounted to 108,252 cases (2022: 101,095), representing a 7.1% increase compared to the previous year. This is due to the steady growth of the oncology patient population, improved standardization of oncology care, and the development of palliative and restorative services.

At the end of 2023, the absolute number of EC patients who completed specialized treatment was 903, with 319 patients continuing treatment. The following results were obtained in percentages by treatment methods and types. 41.0% of patients received surgical treatment alone, 30.1% received combined treatment, 19.8% received comprehensive treatment, 3.4% received radiation therapy alone, 3.1% received drug therapy alone, and 1.8% received chemotherapy and radiation therapy alone.

Next, regarding the five-year survival rate of patients. Regarding EC, at the end of 2023, 12,703 people, or 63.8 per 100,000 population, were registered for dispensary care (at the end of 2022, 12,265 patients, or 62.9 per 100,000 population, respectively); this ranks third among all nosological forms of malignant neoplasms.

Moreover, the mortality rate of the observed cohorts in 2023 was 2.1% (2.0% in 2022).

The five-year survival rate of patients with EC was 65.2% in 2023 (65.8% the previous year) [14].

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that

EC occupies a significant place among all existing malignant tumors in other locations. Despite the small percentage of patients detected at stage IV, given a number of factors, early diagnosis rates are challenging for oncologists. Locally advanced stage III, in addition to its prevalence, carries a high incidence of complications and locoregional metastases, requiring aggressive combination and comprehensive treatment. Furthermore, despite 84.3% of patients being detected at early stages (I-II), the five-year survival rate was 65.2%. The variability and subtlety of symptoms, along with their similarity to various non-core conditions, contribute to the advanced stage of the disease. All of this requires oncologists and oncologists-gynecologists, as well as, first and foremost, primary care providers, obstetricians and gynecologists, and imaging specialists, to increase cancer awareness, educate the public about early symptoms that may indicate this pathology or the onset of proliferative changes, and implement high-tech diagnostic procedures, leading to timely treatment. Women at risk are advised to visit specialized specialists annually and, if necessary, undergo screening.

An epidemiological assessment of the EC situation in our country shows that there are sometimes significant regional differences not only in incidence rates but also in early diagnosis and mortality rates. Therefore, this pathology continues to be a serious problem in modern clinical oncology.

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